

This is a pre-poll and the results will not be saved.

OPERATIONAL RESILIENCE INDEX OF MUSSEL FARMING

Delphi Form 2

Following the consultation issued last July to identify the priority risk scenarios in the mussel aquaculture process in the Arousa Estuary (Delphi 1), this second consultation (Delphi 2) seeks to evaluate the effectiveness of certain factors and tools to address these risk scenarios.

As you know, the Delphi methodology will allow us to find consensus and reach robust conclusions after the exchange of results and the analysis of knowledge and opinions of the panel of experts of which you are a part, with more than 20 actors linked to the mussel sector, the academic field, social agents, administration and the environment. To do this, as in Delphi 1, three rounds of responses will be carried out. After each round you will receive the global and anonymized results of all the experts so that you can reconsider your responses for the next round.

It will only take a few minutes to complete this questionnaire and all your answers will be private and confidential.

The deadline to complete this first round will end on Sunday, October 8, 2023, at 11:55 p.m. (extended hours). If you have any questions or need clarification, you can contact the TransformAr-Galicia team at the email transforma@uvigo.gal or by phone at 986 130 108.

Following an extensive review of scientific literature and exchanges with industry stakeholders at workshops held in Galicia within the TransformAr project, **20 resilience factors** have been identified, classified into **5 dimensions** and with the potential to cope with adverse events of climate change in the field of mussel aquaculture. A matrix for each of the five dimensions will be shown below. Each matrix will present four resilience factors in the rows and the **risk scenarios** identified by the panel of experts in Delphi 1 in the columns.

DIMENSION 1 OF 5: GOVERNANCE

*** 1. Please rate, using a scale between 0 and 3, the extent to which the following governance -related resilience factors (rows) contribute to minimizing the negative impacts caused by each of the following risk scenarios (columns). Each risk scenario is defined by the increase in the indicated climatic-meteorological variable and a phase of the aquaculture process.**

If you wish, you can add additional comments in the following question.

Where 0 = No contribution; 1 = Low contribution; 2 = Medium contribution; 3 = High contribution.

Air Temperature / Obtaining the cheek of the rock zone	Water surface temperature / Collecting rope cheek collection	Water surface temperature / Obtaining the cheek of the rock zone	Water surface temperature / Pre-growing	Water surface temperature / Fattening	Wind / Getting the cheek from the rock area	Acidification / Obtaining the cheek from ropes	Acidification / Obtaining the cheek of zone	Acidification / Stringing	Acidification / Pre-fattening	Acidification / Splitting	Acidification / Fattening	Acidification / Harvest

1.1 Training programs:

Joint training initiatives aimed at regulatory authorities, the productive sector and

					Wind /									
	Air	Water	Water		Getting									
	Temperature	surface	surface	Water	the	cheek	Acidification	Acidification						
	/ Obtaining	temperature	/ Obtaining	surface	Water	from	/ Obtaining	/ Obtaining						
	the cheek of	/ Collecting	the cheek	temperature	surface	the	cheek from	the cheek of						
	the rock	rope cheek	of the rock	/ Pre-	temperature	rock	collecting	the rock	Acidification	/ Pre-	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification
	zone	collection	zone	growing	/ Fattening	area	ropes	zone	/ Stringing	fattening	/ Splitting	/ Fattening	/ Harvest	

other key agents on the challenges of climate change and maritime culture that allow them to be provided with tools and knowledge to implement effective adaptation strategies.

1.2 Flexible management:

Use of adaptive management principles, both by public administration and the productive sector, to address

					Wind /									
	Air	Water	Water		Getting									
	Temperature	surface	surface	Water	the	cheek	Acidification	Acidification						
	/ Obtaining	temperature	/ Obtaining	surface	Water	from	/ Obtaining	/ Obtaining						
	the cheek of	/ Collecting	the cheek	temperature	surface	the	cheek from	the cheek of						
	the rock	rope cheek	of the rock	/ Pre-	temperature	rock	collecting	the rock	Acidification	/ Pre-	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification
	zone	collection	zone	growing	/ Fattening	area	ropes	zone	/ Stringing	fattening	/ Splitting	/ Fattening	/ Harvest	

uncertainty with a flexible and agile approach (e.g. iterative decision-making, incorporation of constant feedback and adjustment of assumptions based on the evolution of the scenarios).

1.3 Marine spatial planning:

Introduce into the Maritime Spatial Planning Plans (POEM) strategies that incorporate the evaluation

					Wind /									
	Air	Water	Water		Getting									
	Temperature	surface	surface	Water	the	cheek	Acidification	Acidification						
	/ Obtaining	temperature	/ Obtaining	surface	Water	from	/ Obtaining	/ Obtaining						
	the cheek of	/ Collecting	the cheek	temperature	surface	the	cheek from	the cheek of						
	the rock	rope cheek	of the rock	/ Pre-	temperature	rock	collecting	the rock	Acidification	/ Pre-	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification	Acidification
	zone	collection	zone	growing	/ Fattening	area	ropes	zone	/ Stringing	fattening	/ Splitting	/ Fattening	/ Harvest	

of potential impacts of climate change on mussel aquaculture and other maritime activities, with the aim of preventing conflicts and promoting sustainable coexistence between various sectors.

1.4 Management of public-private funds:
 Assessment of financial needs for the adaptation of

Air Temperature / Obtaining the cheek of the rock zone	Water surface temperature / Collecting rope cheek collection	Water surface temperature / Obtaining the cheek of the rock zone	Water surface temperature / Pre-growing	Water surface temperature / Fattening	Wind / Getting the cheek from the rock area	Acidification / Obtaining the cheek from collecting ropes	Acidification / Obtaining the cheek of the rock zone	Acidification / Stringing	Acidification / Pre-fattening	Acidification / Splitting	Acidification / Fattening	Acidification / Harvest
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the sector with the aim of efficiently creating and managing public-private funds that allow preventive actions to be carried out and/or cover future contingencies.

2. If you wish, you can add any comments or clarifications you consider relevant to the content of the matrix you have covered.

We remind you that on this occasion, as a measure of flexibility, you can **pause the questionnaire and continue it at another time** . To do so, after completing one of the questionnaire matrices, click on **the 'Next' button** (to save the answers) and then on the **'Pause' button on the next page** (both at the bottom of each page). **You can resume the questionnaire from the 'Start' button in the invitation email.**

Following "

Pause

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